

➤ The benefits of including preprints in Journal Clubs

Help the authors strengthen their work

The feedback will be useful to authors to improve their work before publication.

Discuss science as it happens

It centers the discussion on the research that is being developed right now.

Help raise your and your group's profile

Post the reviews publicly to gain visibility for your work, share the comments with the authors to open opportunities for interactions.

No restrictions on papers to include

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Focus on the science

Move away from the impact factor and focus on the individual paper and on teaching and learning critical skills.

Infographics by ASAPbio Fellows:

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